

IMPROVING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF HOUSEHOLD AND PEASANT FARMS

Nazarov Ibrohim Hasan ugli

Student of direction “Land cadastre and land use” of TIAME NRU Bukhara
Institute of Natural Resources Management

Annotation: In this article, the issues of the development of household and peasant farms, rational and efficient use of land plots, free and independent management of household farms, the development of household farms, attention and support of household farms from the state are particularly touched upon.

Keywords: peasant land, household plot, economic efficiency, household plot services, landowners, agricultural products, cluster land plot.

Today, the worldview of landowners is changing. Interested in employment. The most important thing is to use your backyard effectively. Many people earn good money. The employment of family members and women is especially ensured. Subsequently, systematic work is being carried out to effectively use the lands allocated to peasant farms and owners of household plots, protect their rights and legitimate interests, increase employment and living standards of the rural population. With this in mind, from January of this year, those who used the infield for certain types of activities will be classified as official positions, and this period will be included in their work experience. What are the rules of the system's behavior? Citizens who are engaged in exactly that activity will be classified as officially employed. These activities are: livestock, greenhouse, poultry farming, rabbit

breeding, beekeeping, fishing, gardening, lemon growing and floriculture. This means that citizens who carry out activities in the backyard in this direction will be classified as officials. In our country, 5.5 million people cultivate more than 502.8 thousand hectares of land at the disposal of landowners. Households account for 80% of potatoes grown in our country, 71% of vegetable products, 55-60% of melons, grapes and fruits, and more than 94% of livestock products.

On the basis of the decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on April 26, 2018 on “improvement of the activities of farm farmers and land owners” and on June 30, 2020 on additional measures to increase the efficiency of the use of population plots, 651 “Household Service” LLC were established in our country. Farmers and residents are becoming a real support of the population in organizing the effective use of tomato land by ”household service” enterprises, plowing of tomatoes, promoting cultivation, supplying guaranteed seedlings, local and mineral fertilizers, building compact greenhouses, receiving and processing grown products, delivery to domestic markets and export. The amount of crop grown as a result of doing business with the aim of obtaining crops 2-3 times a year, realizing that from year to year the tomato is an additional source of income. By storing agricultural products in artificially cooled warehouses rather than storing them in ordinary warehouses, the possibility of maximizing the weight of the product increases. Taking into account such factors, special attention is paid to creating sufficient conditions for the delivery of grown products to the table of our people throughout the year.

Today, the state's attention is focused on reducing poverty, providing the necessary resources to generate income and organizing the effective use of household lands, thereby increasing the amount of food on the market and maintaining the stability of the price range. Previously, obtaining a preferential loan for the use of the

estate was up to 3 years. The population will suffer even before it receives income. Now, by the decision of the president, the loan repayment has stretched for 7 years. If we build a greenhouse on 0.01 acres of land worth 10 million soums, it will cost 130-140 thousand. sum per month for 7 years. It will be a huge relief for the citizens. From the infield, you can use the harvest up to 2-3 times. At the same time, in order to create amenities for the population, issues of sustainable water supply for household plots and farms located in areas with heavy water supply were considered.

According to the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, on June 30, 2020, the decision was approved for the purpose of pumping out of the population and water in areas with heavy water supply. The decision set out to cover 70% of the cost incurred for a small-scale artezan well in an amount not exceeding 50 times the base calculation for drilling and commissioning a vertical water well of more than 10 meters. In order to make the population more comfortable and light, the foundation also supports the company “Household service” LLC. The primary responsibilities of the “Household service” are to provide close support to landowners, and to assist in the storage and finding of buyers of vegetables grown by them. The activities of services on the lands where the enterprises of the “Household service” were established were in one way or another. For example, with the construction of a greenhouse in some budding service, some agro techniques are shown and their needs are observed to expand from year to year. As of 2020, cluster method population support has begun. Clusters work with the population Daily. Of the goods that are high in consumption, there is an incubator route in the “Household service” with the aim of stabilizing these products mainly for dairy, meat, eggs, poultry routes. In doing so, the Chick opening is to deliver them to the household of

the population at a low price based on their requirements, and the landlords grow eggs and meat on their territory and resell them in the “Household service”.

As a result of the establishment of lemon cultivation in greenhouses established by the population in apartments, raising chickens from 100 heads, in 2017 an additional 1.2 thousand hectares of lemonarium were built, 3.2 million per 32 thousand households. ta 90 days of chicken distributed 2.3 million. egg production was achieved. Also, planting of fruit seedlings useful for human health, such as Greek nuts, unabi, was organized. The main thing is that as a result of the neglect of citizens in the use of land attached to them as an additional source of income, the failure of a full-fledged formation of land use culture, the non-economic mechanism of responsibility for cases of land use in industry laws is not strictly defined, there are cases of inefficient use of 18.9 thousand hectares of Studies conducted in 2018 found that 4.0 thousand hectares were not planted by 69.4 thousand tomato landowners in the Republic, including 995 hectares in Samarkand region, 649 hectares in Surkhandarya region, 624 hectares in Kashkadarya region, 384 hectares in Navoi region, 294 hectares in Andijan region, 215 hectares in Khorezm region and 323 hectares in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Household land plot is a land allocated in accordance with the procedure and amounts established by law, which is inherited for life by one of the family members for the purpose of free trade and cultivation of agricultural products for the needs of the family, as well as individual housing construction and home improvement.

Household farming is a labor activity related to the cultivation of agricultural products on household land plots both for free trade and for the needs of the family. Household farming is not considered an entrepreneurial activity and does not require state registration of household farming. A person who independently carries out

activities based on participation in personal work on growing agricultural products in a household can obtain the status of a self-employed person in accordance with the procedure established by the legislation on employment of the population. Activities in the household are based on the personal work of the owner of the household land and his family members. For the purposes of household management, free trade and production of agricultural products for the needs of the family before the entry into force of this law on agricultural lands, forest lands and land plots provided from the lands of settlements on the right of lifelong inherited ownership, on the right of individual housing construction and on the right of lifelong inherited for the improvement of residential premises, you can use the provided land plots. The social tax may be paid by the owner or members of his family of a household plot of land with an area of at least 0.04 hectares, occupied on a household plot of land or containing at least fifty heads of cattle or poultry on this plot. At the same time, the owner of an individual household plot of land or his family members pay social tax on a voluntary basis. According to the law, a subsidiary farm is considered to be a labor activity related to the cultivation of agricultural products on household land plots both for free trade and for the needs of the family. At the same time, the household is not included in business activities and does not require state registration. Of course, this is a great opportunity and privilege for the population.

From residential, industrial, household and other premises, as well as vehicles and agricultural machinery located on a household plot of land inherited on the right of lifelong ownership in the management of a household, things, equipment, farm animals, bees, poultry, silkworm (cocoon) and other property-the property can be used. The rights and obligations of persons using household land plots for household farming are also established. In particular, they have the right to freely and

independently manage household farms, including freely selling grown and independently processed agricultural products, independently setting prices and disposing of the income received.

The accounting of household farms is conducted by the self-government bodies of citizens by forming a register of household farms. It reflects information about the owner of an individual household, the area of the household land plot, the number of farm animals, bees, birds and silkworms, as well as the number of agricultural machinery, equipment, vehicles. The wider implementation of the system to increase the income of the population, occupies a special place in providing employment and meeting the demand for food. Thus, the effective use of household plots and arable land by the population is becoming important to fully meet the domestic demand for food in our country, increase incomes and well-being of the population.

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